

HIGHER MARINE EDUCATION ORGANIZATION OF THE MODERN PARADIGM

*The article describes the organization of maritime education in Ukraine. The **purpose** of the article is to analyze the organization of higher maritime education processes.*

Methodology. *Changes in society affect changes in education as well as changes in education affect changes in society. In today's society, higher education requires a combination of professional and academic training. Such changes have been affected by socio-economic changes in the world. However, in the light of changes in the current education system, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of higher education in Ukraine in general and maritime education in particular. The article highlights the main aspects of the formation of education, the impact of that society on the transfer of knowledge and the impact of that knowledge on the development of society.*

Scientific novelty. *The transition of higher education institutions to maritime education is relatively at the initial level, so there is a need to study in detail the structure of transition from traditional to modern, using technologies set by the demand of the labor market.*

Conclusions. *Today, it requires highly skilled marine professionals. Particular attention is paid to the combination of practical skills and critical thinking. Such significant changes in demand have led to changes in higher education. Changed the means of submission of material and methods of processing a given material. Students are now able to work out practical problems to solve certain problems. The communicative aspect plays an important role. All this in combination makes it possible to take a leading role among the workers in the maritime industry. There is a need to modernize curricula, taking into account the combination of practical activities, academic and self-study. Such changes are irreversible and necessary in today's maritime space.*

Key words: *maritime education, social and communication competence, maritime education, higher education, globalization.*

Nowadays, according to the requirements of the International Convention on the Training, Certification of Seafarers and Watchkeeping (STCW/95), the need for naval specialists with a high level of social and communication competence. This is due to the characteristics of the profession itself, the requirements for the professional mobility of seafarers and the international market for their work. In particular, judicial officers should not only have the appropriate professional knowledge and practical skills, but also have an effective management of the judicial staff, in particular maintaining an atmosphere of understanding, mutual assistance, observance of generally accepted moral standards and human relations, and concern for other judicial staff crew members. In addition, as a result of the processes of cultural, scientific, economic integration and globalization, navy professionals work in joint international crews or provide for the operation of foreign vessels, where the main means of interpersonal or group communication, functional communication are professional. For this reason, the specialists, in accordance with their functional responsibilities, must be able to communicate with both crew members and foreign passengers, representatives of the port authorities, and, if necessary, cooperate with law enforcement agencies in other countries; to communicate with citizens who have excellent social traditions, language culture, etc. during the voyage. An analysis of the latest research and publications in which the problem is solved and which the author relies on.

Communicative and competent approach means the ability to use the acquired knowledge and skills in situations where you need to act quickly. During the changes in the maritime higher education system, one of the leading places was occupied by the English language. In the international labor market, English is an integral part of the work of seafarers. Since Ukraine gained independence, the maritime industry has entered the world

market. This led to changes in working conditions, including changes in crew. There is an urgent need for communication between crew members, between other ships and between ship and shore. Such factors have led to significant changes in the teaching of English and the use of teaching techniques. Thus, during English lessons, students must acquire not only translation or grammatical knowledge, but also specialized knowledge of a particular problem, be able to solve questions, give clear instructions, or clearly understand and execute them.

The problem of forming social and communicative competence has repeatedly attracted the attention of scientists. In sociology and social philosophy (J. Locke, T. Hobbes, E. Durkheim, M. Weber, M. Berdyaev, P. Sorokin, T. Parsons) social and communicative competence is considered as a manifestation of purely human, as one of the most valuable social entities, as a basic condition of social life and a means of creating social values. Representatives of communicative philosophy (Yu. Habermas, K. Apel, H. Gadamer, K. Cherry, etc.) pay attention to the importance of a new ethics of human relations, focusing on universal values that would contribute to the understanding of humanity. In pedagogy, social and communicative competence is interpreted as one of the most important necessary for life in society, emphasizing that a person can «happen», realize only in constant contact with others, because of tolerant attitude to other people and thoughts. N. Bibik, I. Ermakov, J. Delors, E. Zeer, O. Ovcharuk, O. Pometun, J. Raven, V. Hutmacher necessarily distinguish social and communicative competence among other key competences. Some aspects of the formation of social and communicative competence of future navigators are covered by S. Butenko, S. Kozak, M. Kulakova, O. Popova, I. Sokol, L. Stupina, V. Chernyavskaya and others. However, despite a rather wide range of scientific works on the study of social and communicative competence, there is no comprehensive study of its formation in future mariner in the process of studying humanities. **The purpose** of the article is to analyze the organization of higher maritime education processes.

Due to the reform of the education system, it becomes necessary to develop a specific global strategy for the training of marine professionals, who are able to adapt continuously to changing conditions of professional activity. Marine professionals should be capable of lifelong learning. There is a need for continuous improvement of the education system. The laws of Ukraine «On Education», «On Higher Education» indicate the provision of general professional training of a specialist, as well as his specialization, aimed at a certain type of activity in specific conditions. Requirements for marine professionals are defined in international conventions and declarations that affect strategic documents, and are major educational areas for countries in the world and for Ukraine. The quality of higher education influences the reorganization of maritime education and higher education in general. Therefore, one of the main strategies is to design vocational training and skills for national maritime education systems. The quality of higher education influences the reorganization of maritime education and higher education in general. One of the main strategies is the design of vocational training and the acquisition of national maritime education systems. This strategy enables the future marine specialist to independently engage in a person-centered professional development process.

There is a need to consider the education system in terms of time. Since the beginning of the 1990s, attention to humanitarian knowledge, to various aspects of the formation of social and communicative competence as a component of professional training of specialists has become noticeable. This is due to the changes in society and the growing importance in it of people, the transition from command-administrative system of management of production processes and human resources. Today it is obvious that for the effective organization of work the importance of the issue of management of organizations, establishing cooperation to achieve the goals of the organization, enriching the full potential of human resources, in particular intellectual, moral and psychophysical. Effectiveness of joint activity depends on the parity of participation of all participants in the production process, their cohesion and general interpersonal relationships. V. Torsky and V. Topalov in the works «Culture of safety in navigation» and «Management of ship crews» note that one of the priority areas in navigation, which allows to reduce the accident of the fleet, damage to the environment and traumatism of people, is a culture of safety that directly related to crew relations. Researchers say that officers must not only have the appropriate professional knowledge and practical skills, but also be able to care about the health and safety of other crew members, ensure compliance with applicable disciplinary rules, maintain an atmosphere of mutual understanding, in the crew team moral standards and human relations, that is, to effectively manage maritime staff [2, p. 5]. It can be stated that, according to the majority of researchers (S. Voloshinov, A. Leontiev, V. Torsky, V. Topalov, V. Chernyavsky), social and communication competence is one of the most important components of navigator's professionalism. Historically, in all countries of the world, the education and training of marine professionals has been closely linked to the training of production personnel. International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers continues to maintain a professional approach to organizing the education and training of seafarers. The approach focuses on minimum requirements for knowledge, understanding and skills, as well as methods for demonstrating competencies and criteria for assessing them. In order to avoid a sharp decline in demand for the maritime profession, maritime institutes were forced to rapidly modernize the educational process. An important component of reducing the attendance was the inability to work onshore with a seafarer diploma. In this regard, maritime higher education institutions have changed their approach to graduation.

The nature of the professional activity of the seafarer is a system of communications, which requires him social and communicative qualities and skills. In its historical and organizational form, the institution of higher education has always addressed fundamental questions about human interests, values and requests. Attention has always been drawn not only to physical or biological features, but also to psychological and existential ones.

Modern researchers pay special attention to the problem of creating an educational and educational environment of the educational institution (I. Zakharov, S. Malan, K. Kretchetnikov) and to the issues of functioning of the educational environment of the higher educational institution (E. Mamontov, L. Koife, T. Meng). The institution of higher education is considered in terms of perspectives in education, society, politics and economics. Higher education institutions are not only scientific and educational centers, but also repositories of socially relevant modern knowledge and competences.

The success of professional interaction as well as of role and interpersonal interaction depends on social and communicative competence. The effectiveness of solving many problems of professional activity depends on the ability of the specialist to interact with other people. Today, in the philosophy of education, attention to the problems of the formation of social and communicative competence in the future specialists is connected with the need for better preparation for professional activity, for life in a constantly changing world. The present socio-cultural reality is very variable, multivariate, plural. I. Predborskaya believes that new, unconventional alternative approaches are needed, which would allow to move away from the unambiguous definition of reality, to move from a linear, unambiguous interpretation of it to the study of all its diversity [3, p. 22].

The current stage requires a transition from learning that provides reproductive perception, linear thinking, to learning that shapes search orientations, creativity, probabilistic thinking [1]. The reluctance to adhere only to a cognitively-oriented, technocratic, inherently educational paradigm, which is predominantly focused on reproductive knowledge, the formation of a certain amount of knowledge, skills and abilities through the accumulation of educational material, is evident.

Any education should be considered in the context of society and evaluated according to its impact on the individual. Education, as both legislation and the labor market, is a key tool for social change as a factor in the formation of social norms [5, p. 214]. In order to optimize education and obtain the desired results, it is necessary to take into account the social norms and market systems of a particular country, which are factors in shaping social behavior and overall socialization of young people. Therefore, higher education is not only a product of social change, but also a source of change. Over time, the concepts of the main task of higher education have changed. The skills of deductive reasoning and logical thinking remained unchanged. However, society constantly demanded that higher education institutions have a practical orientation and specialization of graduates. Based on this need, higher education has evolved towards the pursuit of practical goals, which include the overriding task of adapting constant socio-economic demands to radical changes in science and culture of thought [6, p. 4].

The traditional paradigm of education, formed under the «influence of philosophical and pedagogical ideas, formulated at the end of the eighteenth – early nineteenth century by J. Komensky, J. Pestalozzi, J. Herbart, A. Disterweg, J. Dewey and others. [4, p. 13]. According to I. Predborskaya, the nature of such a paradigm of education is contrary to the needs of humanization [4, p. 14]. Nowadays, social and cultural knowledge are more important, which determine the relationship between people, person and the world [4, p. 23]. The modern specialist is first and foremost a person, prepared for the trials, for a change in lifestyle, it is an educated person, that is, a person of culture, educated, able to preserve and enhance cultural potential. It should also be noted that in times of information civilization, the formation of a moral personality is extremely important. We can see that today social self-determination of a person is determined not only by a fundamentally new technological way of reproducing the whole system of social relations, but also by the nature of forming and maintaining relations between people [2, p. 56].

At the beginning of the 21st century, higher education is focused on narrow-minded components, taking into account the requirements of employers. Increased attention to professional knowledge and skills, which are the main qualities of a modern specialist in the maritime industry. In this context, maritime education has become one of the foremost in the educational space of higher education institutions, which has a mix of empirical and highly professional components in the system to ensure that its graduates meet the requirements of industry. The redevelopment of the goals and objectives of higher education institutions has become the new result-oriented education paradigm. The new paradigm combines research results and a focus on narrow professional outcomes. Educators develop critical thinking and cognitive skills that meet the requirements of professional standards to the level of competence of specialists. Maritime education is globalized and international, which necessitates the constant adaptation to professional and technological progress. Another of the changes needs is modern technology, which is becoming increasingly complex. Crew and ship safety requirements have increased. Much attention is paid to the problem of environmental pollution. All of these factors make it necessary for marine education to adopt a mixed academic-professional approach in the educational process. The academic approach is different from the previous approach and involves lifelong learning. Specific tasks of the professional approach are offered for the development of critical thinking. The blended learning approach combines the opportunity to receive working maritime diplomas in parallel with

educational diplomas. This is in line with the social goals of sailors and gives them the opportunity to study and gain career.

Higher maritime education institutions combine curricula in such a way that training practice and education are responsive to the needs of industry and employers. However, it should be noted that curricula differ from country to country. The reason for this is the difference between the national education standards of each country and the requirements of production. Despite the benefits of the new maritime education paradigm, there are some challenges that need to be addressed. Such challenges include the design and implementation of curricula, taking into account the availability of qualified scientific and pedagogical staff and instructors, the ratio of time to training and its content, the approach to the assessment of acquired competences.

Therefore, the modern social system puts forward new objective requirements to the individual: high level of professionalism, broad knowledge in the sphere of culture, observance of norms of morality, responsibility for the results of its activity, etc. Increasing the interdependence of people in modern society requires more complex social, political and economic interaction between them through a variety of ways of communication [2, p. 56].

We can summarize that modern institutions of higher marine education are making a gradual transition. Degree marine education from ordinary seaman to captain is offered. Future marine professionals have the opportunity to independently decide their position among the educational recipients. They are adapted to change in today's society. Such students have advanced critical thinking skills and well-developed cognitive skills. All this makes it possible to train quality and modern specialists who are competitive in the labor market. Today, it requires highly skilled marine professionals. Particular attention is paid to the combination of practical skills and critical thinking. Such significant changes in demand have led to changes in higher education. Higher maritime education and higher education in general are of great importance for the formation of a capable, competitive specialist. Historically, education has been transformed depending on the needs of society. Maritime education is directly dependent on international conventions and codes, which on the one hand balances the requirements for marine professionals and on the other hand complicates the reorganization of higher maritime institutions. Changed the means of submission of material and methods of processing a given material. Students are now able to work out practical problems to solve certain problems. The communicative aspect plays an important role. All this in combination makes it possible to take a leading role among the workers in the maritime industry. There is a need to modernize curricula, taking into account the combination of practical activities, academic and self-study. Such changes are irreversible and necessary in today's maritime space.

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СУЧАСНА ПАРАДИГМА ОРГАНІЗАЦІЇ ВИЩОЇ МОРСЬКОЇ ОСВІТИ

У статті описані шляхи організацію вищої морської освіти в Україні. **Мета статті** – проаналізувати організацію процесів вищої морської освіти.

Методика. Зміни в суспільстві впливають на зміни в освіті, що є взаємозалежним, тобто зміни в освіті впливають на зміни в суспільстві. У сучасному суспільстві вища освіта вимагає поєднання професійної та академічної підготовки. На такі поєднання вплинули соціально-економічні зміни у світі. Однак, зважаючи на зміни в сучасній системі освіти, необхідно звернути увагу на розвиток вищої освіти в Україні загалом та морської освіти зокрема. У статті висвітлено основні аспекти становлення освіти, вплив суспільства на передачу знань та вплив знань на розвиток суспільства.

Наукова новизна. Перехід вищих навчальних закладів морської освіти на сучасний лад знаходиться відносно на початковому рівні, тому існує необхідність детально вивчити структуру переходу від традиційної до сучасної системи освіти, використовуючи технології, задані попитом на світовому ринку праці.

Висновки. На сучасному ринку праці потрібні висококваліфіковані морські фахівці, які відповідають заданим характеристикам, таким як, володіння комунікативно-компетентнісним підходом, вмінням критично мислити та віднаходити шляхи рішення робочих питань, вмінням організувати колектив та вмінням організувати працю. Особлива увага приділяється поєднанню практичних навичок та критичного мислення. Такі значні зміни попиту призвели до змін у вищій освіті. Змінилися засоби подання матеріалу та методи обробки даного матеріалу. Зараз студенти мають змогу опрацювати практичні завдання для вирішення певних проблем. Комунікативний аспект відіграє важливу роль для успішного спілкування у змішаному екіпажі. Все це в поєднанні дає можливість зайняти провідну роль серед працівників морської галузі. Необхідно модернізувати навчальні програми з урахуванням поєднання практичної діяльності, академічної та навчання впродовж всього життя. Такі зміни незворотні і необхідні в сучасному морському просторі.

Ключові слова: морська освіта, вища освіта, вища морська освіта, соціально-комунікативна компетенція, глобалізація.

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